

Distinguishability and Quantum Mechanics

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Classical physics is often concerned with continuous motion which obeys Newton's second law, allowing one to have motion along straight line paths in one direction. For example, in a classical one dimensional bound state, a particle moves from left to right during one time period and from right to left during another. Thus, there is a notion of the forward motion part of the bound state trajectory and the negative and the two are clearly distinguishable. If a particle's forward motion, however, involves cycling motion including some backward motion, this distinguishability may be lost because a measurement of $-p$ at x does not indicate whether the particle is moving forward or backward i.e. the real part of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are the same. An experiment would need to measure both the real and negative parts of probability, but this does not seem to occur if one simply measures momentum.

Furthermore in a classical stochastic system, a particle may receive a hit and move forward, then move backward etc. One can no longer separate the bound state trajectory into two time reversed pieces. Knowledge of the sign of p at x does not indicate whether the particle is part of an overall forward or negative trajectory. At the same time, one may require that the average energy at each x be consistent with the two time reversed scenarios. In such a case, one may have an average potential $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ etc i.e. if the stochastic hits have some structure they may be represented by an average $V(x)$ leading to an average force. The average $V(x)$ scenario maps into the classical nonstochastic scenario of two time reversed paths for a bound state. Given that the motion is stochastic, one may develop conditional probabilities for p at each x i.e. $P(p/x)$. The conditional probabilities are an average approach, with "interference" or cancellations occurring to allow for averages to match the average $V(x)$ scenario by removing some stochastic effects. The conditional probabilities do not show the exact stochastic motion of the particles. There are also unconditional probabilities like $P(x)$ which do not show explicitly the stochastic changes of p .

We argue that quantum mechanics is such a stochastic system and that problems occur when one tries to impose the idea of continuous particle motion in one direction in time i.e. think that classical paths are distinguishable in all cases. We argue that conditional probabilities capture the stochasticity of the problem leading to the addition of wavefunctions for different paths, (an "or" situation with conditional type probabilities). as the wavefunction is related to the stochastic probability. In a quantum bound state, one does not have two time reversed situations describing forward and backward cycles. Similarly, for a two-slit experiment, classical non-stochastic thought suggests that if one does some measurements far from the slit show the straight line path of the particle, then one may predict which slit it enters. If the interaction of the particle with the potential near the slit is stochastic, one has no idea through which slit the particle passes. Furthermore, transverse hits from the potential may lead to the particle hitting the screen at different places. Quantum mechanics, however, does not seem to be simply stochastic classical motion because there appears to be a definite cycling (i.e. wavelength) linked to different p values. It may be that the stochastic forces in nature also deliver momentum hits in such a manner i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, humps which appear in quantum densities are real.

In classical physics, one adds probabilities of distinct scenarios in “or” situations and there is no “interference” because of distinguishability. In quantum mechanics, one adds conditional type probabilities i.e. $W(x)$ for different paths etc and there is interference because $W(x)$ is ultimately used to produce averages needed to remove some stochastic features. For example, in a bound system one may have an average force to the right at x , composed of three forces. The first is $-F_1$ which imparts kinetic energy KE_1 to the left, followed by F_1 which stops the particle, followed by F_2 which gives the particle kinetic energy KE_2 to the right. On average, one has F_2 and only the kinetic energy to the right KE_2 , but a stochastic theory has to account for all three hits and so one has KE_1 , $-KE_1$ and KE_2 i.e. there is even cancellation of kinetic energy, a positive quantity. Thus, the theory may have “strange” cancellations (or interference) at the level of $W(x)$. For example, $[\sum \text{over } p P(p/x) p^2/2m] / W(x)$ may have $\cos(px)$ terms ($a(p)=a(-p)$) which are negative at x for some p , but positive for others.

In this note, we try to investigate some of these ideas.

Free Particle and Interference of Classical Paths

We argue that quantum issues appear with the wavefunction (related to conditional probability) of a free particle, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. If the particle moves forward, one has $\exp(ipx)$ and if backwards, $\exp(-ipx)$. Forward and backward motion are clearly distinguishable in classical physics so why is a complex probability needed to distinguish the two in quantum mechanics? The real part of both is $\cos(px)$ and it is the same. We argue that the two motions are not distinguishable in a simple sense. In other words, more complex motion may be occurring as a particle moves to the right and this motion may involve some backward motion as part of a cycle. For example, there are models of zitterbewegung (1) which describe an electron as moving in a helical pattern. If a forward moving particle has both forward and backward motion which cannot be distinguished at a specific point x say, by the “real” part of the probability ($\cos(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$), but only through the full complex form, then the idea of a classical forward path and its time reversed path is problematic. The two become mixed i.e. $W_1(x)+W_2(x)$ (W =wavefunction) in a conditional probability type “or” situation needed to create a real result. This idea seems also to appear in a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the endpoints. The wavefunction is proportional to $\exp(ipavex)-\exp(-ipavex)$ where $pave$ is an average momentum because many $\exp(ipx)$ “waves” with weight $a(p)$ are stirred up. From the average point of view, it looks as if there are two classical paths, one with $pave$ forward and the other with $-pave$ i.e. backwards motion. The strange complex probability still exists in the average, however, meaning forward and backward motion are not distinguishable in a one-dimensional sense. Thus, the two classical motions which would occur classically at different times have their probabilities add in an “or” sense. The scenario of a two slit experiment also seems to be similar as one adds wavefunctions (related to conditional probability) for two classical paths which classically would occur at different times i.e. be distinguishable. We suggest the adding of classical paths (at the wavefunction probability level) means the paths are not distinguishable (without an extra measurement added which destroys interference). Thus, it seems the notion of distinguishable paths from classical physics does not hold in quantum mechanics if something disrupts this distinguishability. If forward motion involves a kind of cycling including both forward and backwards motion, then a measurement might register backward motion (during the cycle) leading one to think the particle

is moving backward overall. This is not true, so the measurements of p (the real part $\cos(px)$) cannot distinguish between forward and backward motion. In the case of a two slit experiment, a particle is sent in a classical straight line path towards a two slit device, but if stochastic hits occur there, one has no idea through which slit the particle passes and must consider wavefunction (probabilities) in an “or” situation i.e. $W(\text{path1}) + W(\text{path2})$.

Classical Average, Stochastic Hits and Intrinsic Momentum Related Periodicity

We argue that quantum bound states result from stochastic hits from a potential $\sum V(k)\exp(ikx)$ which is $V(x)$ on average, combined with an inherent periodicity related to wavelength of a particle with momentum p . In addition, there exists the constraint that average kinetic energy at each x plus potential energy $V(x)$ equals a constant E (average energy). The form of $V(x)$ is the same as that used in classical physics which suggests the average kinetic energy must behave as classical kinetic energy. Stochastic motion, however, is different. Consider a force $-F1$ which knocks a particle to the left endowing it with a kinetic energy $KE1$. Another force $F1$ a little later brings the particle back to rest and a third force $F2$ gives it a kinetic energy of $KE2$. On average, the force is $F2$ and the kinetic energy changes from 0 to $KE2$, but if one has high time resolution during measurements, one may see $KE1$ as the particle moves to the left etc. Thus, one requires a theory which displays stochastic kinetic energies and momenta (because they can be measured), but at the same time, some of these must vanish in the creation of the average (e.g. kinetic energy average) at x which with $V(x)$ must yield E . A classical kinetic energy term is $pp/2m$, so one must have negative probabilities associated with $pp/2m$ at some x points. Thus, it seems one is interested in $P(p/x)$ i.e. a conditional probability. Furthermore, there appears to be an intrinsic periodicity because a kinetic energy of $pp/2m$ may be positive at some x , but negative at others e.g. $KE1$. This periodicity may be different for different momentum p values.

If a particular momentum p is positive in a certain x range and negative in another, then it seems one should have the sign of the momentum arise from the probability. For example utilizing $\cos(px)$ as a possible periodic function, $p \cos(px)$ with $p > 0$ indicates that in the range 0 to $3.14/2$, momentum is positive, but from $3.14/2$ to $3/2$ (3.14), negative. This probability combines both $+/- p$ probabilities in order to create a real function. If one considers each p separately, there is a complex probability for each ($a(p)=a(-p)$) i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ (if this is the periodic form). Given that one thinks in terms of nonstochastic motion, positive p in a smooth classical sense means motion to the right and $-p$ to the left. The fact that probabilities are complex suggests the two time reversed paths are not distinguishable. The periodic behaviour associated with p is peculiar and must be linked to similar periodicity in the stochastic force or an intrinsic cycling of the quantum particle itself when it has a particular momentum. Thus, there seems to be an inherent periodicity $\exp(ipx)$ associated with p in both particle motion and force. This is possible if force is related to virtual photons which exhibit such periodicity. The complex $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ interfere as complex numbers at x , but that does not mean physical cancellation occurs. Nevertheless, with the interference, there are points where $\cos(px)$ is zero, i.e. one cannot find a momentum of p . Furthermore, the wavefunction $W(x)=\sum$ over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ involves “interference” of different p 's and has zeros itself which become the zeros of the spatial density, a physical observable.

Two Kinds of Probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p/x)$

In quantum bound states, there exist two types of probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p/x)$ and it is important to distinguish between the two. $P(p/x)$ is related to $W(x)$ the wavefunction, while $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$. $W(x)$ considers different stochastic momenta which may be stirred up with different weights at x . These include the two “classical time reversed paths” i.e. a particle moving forward for half of the bound state time and then backwards. Thus, if there are two different paths available, say in a two slit experiment, one should add probabilities at the $W(x)$ level even though $W(x)$ is more like a partition function and not at the $W(x)W(x)$ level. I.e. $W_{\text{total}} = W_1 + W_2$ followed by: $W_{\text{total}}*W_{\text{total}}$ and not $W_1*W_1 + W_2*W_2$.

Due to stochasticity, one does not really have the two classical paths, except in one’s mind. As an example, consider a two slit experiment. A particle is sent in a straight line trajectory towards one slit and soft measurements are done to ensure its direction far away from the slits. Classical reasoning suggests the particle should travel in a straight line and pass through the slit in its path. If the solid portion of the slit system, however, represents a potential delivering stochastic hits, the particle will receive momentum components parallel to the two slit surface and one has no idea through which slit it passes, or even the momentum parallel to the slit system. Thus, one must consider paths from each slit in a probability or situation using W_1+W_2 . In other words, there is “interference” between the two conditional probability-like pieces to cancel out stochastic parts which should not be part of the average result. If one used $W_1(x)W_1(x) + W_2(x)W_2(x)$ instead, this would imply that one knows that the particle is following one path or the other, but one does not have this information. By making a measurement to confirm through which slit a particle passes, destroys the physical interference pattern.

To see this more clearly, consider that in the high energy limit, quantum spatial density $W_1(x)W_1(x)$ is said to match classical density $dx/v(x)$ (where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$). In the classical case, there are clear forward and backwards portions to the bound state. Using $W_1(x)W_1(x)$, it seems, allows for the same kind of scenario while $P(p/x)$ and $W(x)$ do not.

Classical reasoning assumes non-stochastic distinguishable motion, but this reason is applied to stochastic systems (and others) which do not have this distinguishability. In the case of a bound state particle, $V(x)$ appears in the average result, so one reasons in terms of the classical bound state and its two time reversed paths.

Measurements

One may wonder why there exist two types of probabilities. The relative conditional probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is used to create the wavefunction by taking a sum or considering “or” conditions, so it is the $W_i(x)$ that add. If is interested in an average at x , one may use $f(p) a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, but “taking” a measurement, even if it is done internally by the system, suggests a particle may switch from p_1 to p_2 at x . If one uses relative conditional probabilities, it seems there is another average, namely $a(p_i)\exp(i p_i x) f(p) a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $W(x)$ in the denominator is dropped because a new normalization is needed. This, however, may be written as: $P(x)P(p/x)$ where $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ (for the bound state). Thus, $W(x)$ gives rise to a $P(x)$ or spatial density.

Alternatively, a particle at x with p_1 may receive a stochastic hit and change to p_2 yielding a new product relative conditional probability $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$.

Nevertheless, it is the W_i that add as “or” conditions and one may create a $(\sum W_i) / (\sum W_i)$ to obtain the new density average.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum bound states are based on relative conditional probabilities $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ with $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. $W(x)$ the normalization constant (wavefunction) is obtained by summing over all relative conditional probabilities. Thus, if one has alternative paths as in a two slit experiment, one would add W_i . We argue that some conceptual issues may arise (as in the two slit experiment) if one thinks in terms of non-stochastic distinguishable classical paths as opposed to stochastic motion or cycling motion, say zitterbewegung. For example, for non-stochastic classical physics, a particle may move in a straight line which should pass through the slit in its path. If stochastic interactions occur at the slit potential (material around the slits), one has no idea through which slit the particle passes and must use conditional probability ideas which handle such stochasticity, but also allow for “interference” as some stochastic effects cancel with each other. In a bound state system, some $p/2m$ $P(p/x)$ become negative while others are positive (if one considers $-p/p$ combined to give $2\cos(px)$). In the case of zitterbewegung, a particle with momentum p may move in a somewhat complicated motion which involves positive and negative motion even though and average the particle only moves forward. If one considers only a point x and the real part of $\exp(ipx)$, one may not distinguish between forward $\exp(ipx)$ and backward $\exp(-ipx)$ motion. One may, however, calculate an average kinetic energy (and obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation) from considerations taking only at one x point.

The idea of $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ seems to arise when one considers a relative conditional probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which receives say a stochastic hit from $V(x)$ or an internal measurement) changing it to p_2 . Then, one has a product relative conditional probability $a(p)\exp(ipx) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ which gives rise to a new probability that needs to be normalized and seems to match experiments where one performs a measurement which may change the conditional relative probability p to p_2 without destroying the quantum system. Thus, one may calculate an average $P(x)P(p/x) f(p)$ (summing on x and p) and obtain results matching experiments, although the root probability seems to be associated with $P(p/x)$ with $W(x)$ being used in “or” situations.

References

1. Niehaus, A. Zitterbewegung and the Election (2017) <https://arxiv.org/abs/1701.02998>